

PCT ped - cut-off < 2

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Cut-off	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Calo' Carducci 2014	36	6	5	17	0.55	0.88 [0.74, 0.96]	0.74 [0.52, 0.90]
Groselj-Grenc 2009	20	3	4	9	0.28	0.83 [0.63, 0.95]	0.75 [0.43, 0.95]
Pourakbari 2010	37	52	20	46	0.5	0.65 [0.51, 0.77]	0.47 [0.37, 0.57]
Simon 2008	20	25	5	14	0.5	0.80 [0.59, 0.93]	0.36 [0.21, 0.53]

PCT ped - cut-off = 2/2.5

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Cut-off	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Pourakbari 2010	25	20	32	78	2.0	0.44 [0.31, 0.58]	0.80 [0.70, 0.87]
Simon 2008	17	10	8	29	2.5	0.68 [0.46, 0.85]	0.74 [0.58, 0.87]

PCT test ped - cut-off > 2.5

Study	TP	FP	FN	TN	Cut-off	Sensitivity (95% CI)	Specificity (95% CI)
Pourakbari 2010	17	11	40	87	10.0	0.30 [0.18, 0.43]	0.89 [0.81, 0.94]
Simon 2008	13	7	12	32	5.0	0.52 [0.31, 0.72]	0.82 [0.66, 0.92]

